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compass

COMPUTATIONAL PHYSICS FOR ASPIRING SCIENTISTS

Proceedings

2023 Physics Club's Final Project

October 16 - November 4, 2023

P.16

DAMPING OF QUARTER CAR PASSIVE SUSPENSION SYSTEM

AC CIRCUIT

AUTOMOTIVE ENGINEERING

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PHYSICS CLUB
OCTOBER STEM SCHOOL

2023 Physics Club's Final Project

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Computational Physics for Aspiring Scientists

December 3, 2024

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Chapter 1

Introduction

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1.1 Overview of Computational Physics

Computational physics bridges theoretical predictions and experimental observations through the solution of complex physical problems using computer algorithms and simulations. It really changed the face of physics in trying to tackle some very complex phenomena otherwise so very hard or even impossible to analyze analytically, especially when the equations become too complicated to be solved by hand. With the great growth of power in computation, it is gradually becoming an essential pillar of modern science for the simulation of everything from subatomic particles to galaxies and beyond.

Widely recognized as the “third pillar” of scientific investigation, computational physics stands alongside theoretical and experimental physics as a core method for advancing knowledge. As the physicist John von Neumann famously put it, “The sciences do not try to explain, they hardly even try to interpret, they mainly make models.” In that one sentence, in a nutshell, that’s what computational physics has been all about enabling modeling, testing against reality, and investigating what otherwise would be impossible.

The origins of Computational Physics evolved during the mid-years of the past century with the development of electronic computers. By the 1940s physicists began to use computers to solve two of the most intractable scientific problems of the day: atomic calculations and neutron diffusion in nuclear reactors. One of the important early projects was the Monte Carlo method devised by Stanislaw Ulam and John von Neumann while working on the Manhattan Project. It relies on random sampling for simulating systems that are complex in nature. These modern computational techniques have thus been founded in physics.

1.2 Importance of these topics in physics and engineering

In the ensuing decades, computational physics expanded into a variety of research areas. Computational models of fluid dynamics, statistical mechanics, quantum systems, and astrophysics became commonplace in the 1960s and 1970s. In each field, new methods had to be developed appropriately to solve the particular types of equations and problems presented by the various branches of physics. By the 1980s, computational physics emerged as a distinct field itself, with its own proprietary software, dedicated supercomputers, and a cadre of people working on nothing but computational methods.

Nowadays, computational physics is still one of the most important revolutionary tools in the process of scientific discovery. It allows for the simulation of climate patterns, the prediction of material properties, the modeling of biological processes, and probing into the essential forces of the universe in ways that were previously unimaginable. As Richard Hamming, a computational physicist, once said, "The purpose of computing is insight, not numbers." This approach has given scientists amazing insights into familiar and mysterious areas of the natural world.

1.3 Purpose of the Book

We are very pleased to be able to show in this book some of the outstanding work produced by our members during the past year. This volume includes some remarkable projects chosen from our calculus-based physics course, and it serves as a source not only for exhibiting accomplishments but also for students, instructors, and researchers who are just beginning their work in computational physics.

The main purpose of the proceedings is to illustrate how computational tools can bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application for physics and engineering. This season, we asked all our members to do a final project in which they were supposed to apply their understanding of mathematics and physics along with modern technologies of computational physics. The participants had a prolonged enriching experience that started with an intensive training course equipping them with important skills in computational research, computer science, and academic writing.

Through teamwork, members working in groups produced excellent projects, including suspension systems and nonlinear RLC circuits simulations. As an example, one project deals with the investigation of the behavior of active suspension systems with quarter-car models and differential equations, aiming at optimizing comfort and stability. Yet another is on nonlinear RLC circuits, discussing their various oscillatory behaviors, along with their real-world applications of radio tuning circuits and signal filters. These projects show some ways in which computational physics can crack solutions to complex real-world problems in an innovative manner.

The book is a combination of theoretical physics and computational problem-solving, with the illustration of examples and exercises; the tools and techniques are developed to perform modeling and simulation of physical phenomena. Computational science has come to be regarded as the "third pillar" in scientific discovery along with theory and experiment.

This book would not have seen the light of day without critical mentor guidance, whose support was indispensable throughout the program. We would also like to extend our deepest gratitude to all

contributors and collaborators whose efforts have led to this publication.

The STEM October Physics Club proudly presents this collection of works as a testimony to the power of collaboration, perseverance, and innovation in moving the frontier of physics education forward.

Chapter 2

Fundamentals

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2.1 Suspension Systems Fundamentals and Challenge

Necessity of Suspension System

Road vehicles need to maintain a road-wheel contact, but because roads are not perfectly flat, a system to separate the wheel's vertical displacement from the rest of the car is needed. Enter Suspension systems. While suspension systems ensure the wheel to follow the road shape, it also tries to keep the vehicle's body following a straight line, which enhances the ride quality. Suspension systems can achieve these two objectives by dividing the vehicle into two masses by a spring and a damper. The mass suspended by the spring, which should follow a straight line, is called the sprung mass, while the non-suspended mass, which should follow the road shape, is called the unsprung mass.

Mechanism of Suspension System

The system works as following. When a vehicle goes over a bump, the spring compresses, absorbing the shock. If there is no damper, the spring keeps oscillating pushing the sprung mass up and down. Thus, we put a damper to dissipate the spring potential energy into thermal energy. The damper works by pushing a viscous oil through narrow tunnels which generates a huge amount of friction.

Figure 2.1: Simple suspension system

Modelling the Suspension System

For simulating vehicles to test a suspension system, we can use a quarter-car model as shown in Fig.2.

Figure 2.2: Free body diagram of quarter-car model with one degree of freedom

We can use Newton's second law of motion to represent this system mathematically,

$$F_{spring} - F_{damper} = M_s a_s \quad (2.1)$$

$$F_{spring} = -K_s (X_s - X_t) \quad (2.2)$$

$$F_{damper} = b(V_s - V_t) \quad (2.3)$$

where K_s is the stiffness of the spring, b is the damping coefficient, X_t is the road vertical displacement and X_s is the vertical displacement of the sprung mass from its equilibrium point. This system needs 5 input parameters: initial values of X_s , X_t , V_s , V_t as a function of time and, of course, an array of time points, which the system functions within.

Active suspension

In conventional suspension systems, the damping coefficient is fixed for each car, limiting the driving experience for the driver to one driving experience- comfortability or handling. In modern cars, some companies implement advanced adaptive (active) suspension systems. These systems are designed to give the driver the option to change between the comfort and performance suspension system, by offering the option of adjusting the damping coefficient. One of many features of this system is that the system can change the damping coefficient based on the environment the car is moving through.

Feedback mechanism and PID controller

The active suspension system, in this case, will work in a feedback loop as shown in Figure (6) to give the best driving experience. This feedback loop is managed by PID controller, which will be

Figure 2.3: PID controller

discussed in the next section. The PID controller, which stands for Proportional- Integral- Derivative controller, is widely used feedback control system in engineering. This controller is designed and manipulated to regulate a system's behavior by continuously adjusting a control input-based control input to minimize the error between the desired value and the actual value.

2.1.1 Questions

First Problem

Imagine that you are an engineer at Tesla, and you want to understand the effect of changing the damping coefficient in a suspension system on the stability and handling of the car.

1. Find the differential equation that describes this system from equations (1-3) to get the displacement as function of time.
2. Create three graphs for your suspension system, representing critical damping, underdamping, and overdamping oscillations, using parameters listed in table.1 except the damping coefficient. These graphs should illustrate the behavior of your system in response to a road bump condition. The function of tire displacement would be upper half cosine wave, with maximum amplitude of 0.1m, and frequency of 1rad/sec.

Important: In the simulation, you allowed to only change the damping coefficient in each of three graphs, representing different damping scenario. Some variations in the graphs are acceptable.

Second problem

After finishing your first task, your supervisor wants to test your system in a real situation. Your task is to simulate the behavior of your system on harsh road with a lot of small bumps.

1. Plot the displacement of sprung system as function of time, changing only the coefficient damping to get the minimum variation in the displacement of sprung system.
2. Why do you think that this damping coefficient can achieve comfort experience for the driver?

Important The model you will use for the bumps is Square function with 50% pulse width, frequency of 1 rad/sec, and maximum amplitude of 0.05 m.

Variable	Value
M_s	216.75 kg
K_s	21700 N/m
b	1200 N.s/m

Table 2.1: Variables you will need in the simulation

Bonus Question

Your task is to simulate the behavior of your system under conditions of harsh roads using the PID controller to give the driver the best comfortability.

1. Create Hypothetical model for some road bumps. Then plot the displacement of sprung mass as function of time without using PID controller.
2. Intall your PID controller and try to adjust the three parameters: P, I, and D to get the least variation in sprung displacement.
3. Why did you choose these parameters of PID ?

Important: Your method of choosing the three parameters will be based mainly on trail and error.

2.2 Non-linear RLC Circuits Fundamentals and Challenge**Theoretical knowledge**

There are many electrical components used in all circuits: diodes, inductors, resistors, transistors, capacitors, ICs, etc. A circuit that contains an AC power source, a resistor (R), an inductor (L), and a capacitor (C) is called an RLC circuit. The circuit is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2.4: A series RLC circuit

In order to be able to understand the system, we can use energy conservation. The law that is analogous to energy conservation in electricity is called Kirchoff's voltage law. It states that the voltage drops across all the components of the circuit must equal the voltage of the source. In other words, we can say that

$$V_R + V_L + V_C = V_S$$

where V_R is the voltage drop when the current passes through the resistor, V_L is the voltage drop when the current passes through the inductor, V_C is the voltage drop when the current passes through the capacitor, and V_S is the voltage provided by the power source. We can rewrite this expression to better accommodate our case. We know the following relations

$$\Delta V_R = iR$$

$$\Delta V_L = L \frac{di}{dt}$$

$$\Delta V_C = \frac{Q}{C}$$

where i is the current in the circuit, L is the inductance of the inductor (which is a constant), C is the capacitance of a capacitor (which is a constant), and Q is the charge on the plates of the capacitor. Therefore, we can rewrite the relation as

$$iR + L \frac{di}{dt} + \frac{Q}{C} = V_S(t)$$

In computational models of linear RLC Circuits, we need to account for energy loss. A system that loses energy over time is said to be *damped*. There are three types of damped oscillations: underdamped, critically damped, and overdamped. The general differential equation governing an oscillating damped system is

$$\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + 2\gamma\omega_n \frac{dx}{dt} + \omega_n^2 x = 0$$

where ω_n is the natural frequency of the system and γ is a constant. For $\gamma = 0$, the system isn't damped (verify this mathematically). If $0 < \gamma < 1$, the system is underdamped; if $\gamma = 1$, the system is critically damped; if $\gamma > 1$, the system is overdamped.

2.2.1 The Problem

In real life, the voltage drop across a resistor and an inductor varies with higher powers of current. Although the same applies to capacitors, you will only deal with non-linear resistors and non-linear

inductors in this problem. In this case, we write the equation mentioned above as

$$\frac{d\Psi(i)}{dt} + \Gamma(i) + \frac{Q}{C} = V(t)$$

where $V_L = \frac{d\Psi(i)}{dt} = iL(i)$, $V_R = \Gamma(i)$, and $i = \frac{dQ}{dt}$. Notice that the voltage provided by the source varies with time, and Ψ and Γ are both functions of current. Given that

$$\Psi(i) = L_1 i + L_2 i^3 + L_3 i^5$$

$$\Gamma(i) = R_1 i + R_2 i^3 + R_3 i^5$$

$$V(t) = V_o \sin(\omega t)$$

and $i = 1$ and $\frac{di}{dt} = 0$ at $t = 0$, where $R_1, R_2, R_3, L_1, L_2, L_3, V_o, \omega$ are constants, answer the following questions:

1. Find the differential equation that describes this system. Don't assume any values for the given constants.
2. Plot a current versus time graph, assuming that all constants equal 1. Also, plot a current versus change in current graph and notice the oscillating behavior of the system.
3. Study how changing the values of V_o and ω affects the behavior of the system drastically. Try $\omega = \pi$ and $V_o = \frac{1}{\pi}$ and describe what happens to both graphs while using visuals. Try to mention your reasoning if possible.
4. Compare the current versus time graph you got and the graph of a damped oscillator in all three damping cases. State as many differences and similarities as you can between the two systems and their various cases. Use any proper values of ω_n and γ .
5. Describe why we need to study non-linear RLC Circuits and at least one real-life system in which RLC circuits are used. The descriptions should be clear and concise. Extreme conceptual/mathematical details aren't necessary.

2.3 Mathematical and Computational Tools Used

2.3.1 Python

If you are not going to use Python, go to Section 2.3.2.

For coding the model, you will need Python and 3 libraries: Numpy, odeint, and Matplotlib. For the installation of the libraries, separately write each of the following 3 codes in the terminal (CMD) and hit enter.

Terminal

```
>>> py -m pip install numpy
>>> py -m pip install scipy
>>> py -m pip install matplotlib
```

Basics of Libraries

Numpy. It is used to handle and create arrays, which are faster for the computer to handle with. For example, these are lines of codes used to create arrays in Numpy.

Numpy

```
import numpy as np

# Creating an array
my_list=np.array([1,2,3])

# Creating an array with 5 zeros
my_list=np.zeros(5)

# Creating a time space from 0 to 10 sec diveded into 100 point
time_point=np.linspace(0,10,num=100)

# 2 * Average of the absolute values in an array
average=np.average(abs(my_list))*2
```

For further information about Numpy, check [Numpy Documentation](#).

odeint. It is used to solve the differential equations. It is so easy and straightforward. You define a function that takes the initial values and returns an array of velocity and acceleration, respectively

odeint

```
from scipy.integrate import odeint

# Define your initial values
Values=[0., 0.]

# Define our function for acceleration=displacement+velocity/k
def our_function(initial values, time, k):
    x[0],x[1]=Values
    acc=x[0]+x[1]/k
    return np.array([x[1],acc])

solution=odeint(our_function, Values, time_point, args(5.0,))

# solution[:,0] is the array of displacement at eachpoint
# solution[:,1] is the array of velocity at each point
```

For further information about odeint, check [odeint Documentation](#).

Matplotlib. It is mainly used for graphing the results. It is straightforward.

Matplotlib

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

plt.plot(time_point, solution[:, 0] label='displacement(t)')
plt.plot(timp_point, solution[:, 1], label='velocity(t)')
plt.legend(loc='best');plt.xlabel('time');plt.grid();plt.show()
```

2.3.2 MATLAB/SIMULINK

Overview

If you do not have coding experience, you still can do your simulation on MATLAB/Simulink. MATLAB is a programming environment that is primarily used by engineers and researchers for numerical computation, data analysis, and visualization. There are many extensions of MATLAB; one of these is Simulink. Simulink is used for modeling, simulating, and designing dynamic and control systems, depending mainly on your logic to construct logical blocks. Inside Simulink, there is an extension called Simscape that is used to simulate physical systems without any background information about modeling the system. Keep in mind that you are allowed only to use the Simulink features without any other extensions.

Further explanation

Here is an example of simulating differential equations in Simulink. On the main interface, you will find the Library Browser, where you can access blocks for your simulation. Figure(3) illustrates the main blocks you may use for your simulation, and you can learn about the function of each block from the descriptions provided below each block. Now, let's attempt to simulate a hypothetical differential

Figure 2.5: Sample of logical blocks in Library browser

equation.

$$\ddot{X}_s = 1 - 2\dot{x} - 5x \quad (2.4)$$

Where \dot{X}_s is the first derivative, while \ddot{X}_s is the second derivative. First, the main blocks you will use are the integrator, derivative, gain, constant, sum, and scope. Construct the function using your logic, as depicted in Figure (4), where the primary function is created with signal names and block placement. After constructing the function, run the simulation and open the scope to view your results, as illustrated in Figure (5).

Figure 2.6: Simulink Model

Figure 2.7: Graph of simulation

Chapter 3

Suspension System Projects

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3.1 Abdelhakim Fahmy

S Problem One

Explanation

This code solves the differential equation of a suspension system. First, let's look at the model in real life, as shown in Figure 1. To analyze the forces on the tire and on the suspension, use the following free-body diagram(Figure 2). The motion of the sprung mass can be described by the following equations.

$$F_{spring} - F_{damper} = M_s a_s \tag{3.1}$$

$$F_{spring} = -K(x_s - x_t) \tag{3.2}$$

$$F_{damper} = b(v_s - v_t) \tag{3.3}$$

Substituting with 2 and 3 in 1 to find a differential equation that describes the motion of the system, knowing that x_s is the sprung mass displacement and x_t is the tire displacement.

$$M_s \frac{d^2 x_s}{dt^2} = -k(x_s - x_t) - b\left(\frac{dx_s}{dt} - v_t\right) \tag{3.4}$$

Figure 3.1: Simple suspension system

Figure 3.2: Free-body diagram of the simple suspension system

Let's assume that the tire stays in contact with the road, and let's make the road have two bumps, modeling each bump as an upper half cosine function with an amplitude of 0.1 and a frequency of 1, illustrated in Figure 3. Since the tire stays in contact with the road, we can equate the tire

Figure 3.3: Road characteristics

displacement to the piecewise function -the function varies with time; hence, t is used.

$$f(t) \begin{cases} 0 & , 0 < t < \pi \\ 0.1 \cos(t + \frac{\pi}{2}) & , \pi \leq t \leq 2\pi \\ 0 & , 2\pi < t < 5\pi \\ 0.1 \cos(t + \frac{\pi}{2}) & , 5\pi \leq t \leq 6\pi \\ 0 & , t > 6\pi \end{cases}$$

Since we have all the needed info, we can move on to the code. There's a function, `odeint`, that solves differential equations; however, it only solves first-order differential equations; hence, let's define a system of equations that represents the second-order differential equation, and rearrange the mass to separate the acceleration term and substitute with the piecewise function.

$$\frac{dx_s}{dt} = v \quad (3.5)$$

$$\frac{dv}{dt} = \frac{-k}{M_s}(x_s - f(t)) - \frac{b}{M_s}(v - f'(t)) \quad (3.6)$$

Code

```

1 from scipy.integrate import odeint
2 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
3 import numpy as np
4 from scipy.misc import derivative
5
6 M = 216.75
7 K = 21700
8 b = #depending on the graph
9
10 def model(y, t):
11     x, v = y
12     dxdt = v
13     def f(t):
14         if np.pi <= t <= 2 * np.pi:
15             return 0.1 * np.cos(t + np.pi / 2)
16         elif 5 * np.pi <= t <= 6 * np.pi:
17             return 0.1 * np.cos(t + np.pi / 2)
18         else:
19             return 0
20
21     g = derivative(f, t)
22
23     dvdt = - (K/M)*( x - f(t)) - (b / M) * (v - g)
24     return [dxdt, dvdt]
25

```

```
26 y0 = [0, 0]
27 t = np.linspace(0, 30, 200)
28
29 y = odeint(model, y0, t)
30
31 pt.figure(figsize=(10, 4))
32 pt.plot(t, y[:, 0])
33 pt.title('Displacement vs Time')
34 pt.xlabel('Time(s)')
35 pt.ylabel('Displacement(m)')
36
37 pt.grid(True)
38 pt.show()
```

Results

Let's test the system in three conditions: under damping, critical damping, and over-damping to see how it behaves, using the values listed in Table 1. After running the code we get figures 4, 5, and

constant	value
M_s	216.75kg
k	21700N/m
b_c	4337.5N.s/m

Table 3.1: Constants

6 for each case respectively which represent how much time does the system need to get back to equilibrium. In other words, in what case the system is more stable.

Figure 3.4: Underdamping

Figure 3.5: Critical damping

S Problem Two

Explanation

To solve this problem, we will use the same code, but we need to change the tire displacement function (road characteristics) to the new one which is sine bumps with an amplitude of 0.05m and

Figure 3.6: Overdamping

pulse of 50 percent.

$$y = 0.05\sin(2t) \tag{3.7}$$

Now, we define a piecewise function to represent the road, and plotting the graph is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 3.7: piecewise function

Code

```
1 from scipy.integrate import odeint
2 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
3 import numpy as np
4 from scipy.misc import derivative
5
6 M = 216.75
7 K = 21700
8 b_values = [1200, 4337.5, 6000]
9
10 def model(y, t, b):
11     x, v = y
12     dxdt = v
13     def f(x):
14         if 0 <= x <= np.pi/2:
15             return 0.05 * np.sin(2*x)
16         else:
17             return 0
18     g = derivative(f, t)
19     dvdt = - (K/M)*( x - f(t)) - (b / M) * (v - g)
20     return [dxdt, dvdt]
21
22 y0 = [0, 0]
23 t = np.linspace(0, 4, 60)
24
25 plt.figure(figsize=(10, 4))
26
27 for b in b_values:
28     y = odeint(model, y0, t, args=(b,))
29     plt.plot(t, y[:, 0], label=f'b = {b}')
30
31 plt.title('Displacement vs Time')
32 plt.xlabel('Time(s)')
33 plt.ylabel('Displacement(m)')
34 plt.legend()
35 plt.grid(True)
36 plt.show()
```

Results

Now, we run the new code for different damping coefficients; to optimize comfort, we need to find the graph with minimal variations in displacement. As seen in Figure 8, we can observe the

Figure 3.8: Displacement vs Time for road new characteristics

behavior of the sprung mass due to facing the road bump. First, for the under-damped situation, $b = 1200$, the sprung mass oscillates more than in other situations which can cause discomfort for the passengers. Second, for the over-damped situation, although having fewer oscillations, the sprung mass takes more time to adjust and reach equilibrium. Finally, the optimal damping coefficient to ensure a perfect ride would be the critically damped situation; although it gets displaced more than the over-damped from $t = 0$ to $t = 1$, it catches up with over-damping and then surpasses it by going back to equilibrium faster. In summary, critical damping offers the optimal comfort because 1- it restores equilibrium the fastest and 2- it has less oscillations.

Figure 3.9: Displacement vs Time for new critical damping $b = 2150$

The first value of the damping coefficient $b = 4335.7$ was found using the law $b_c = 2\sqrt{k \times m}$. However, critical damping coefficients are found by approximating the value until it exhibits the behavior of a critically damped system which can be seen more in figure 9.

3.2 Ahmed Mamdouh, Mohamed Ahmed

3.3 Question 1

3.3.1 finding the differential equation that describes the displacement

We have that

$$F_{spring} - F_{damper} = M_s a_s \quad (3.8)$$

$$F_{spring} = -K_s (X_s - X_t) \quad (3.9)$$

$$F_{damper} = b(V_s - V_t) \quad (3.10)$$

We can conclude the following equation from the first 3 equations:

$$-K_s (X_s - X_t) - b(V_s - V_t) = M_s a_s \quad (3.11)$$

$$-K_s (X_s - X_t) - b(\dot{X}_s - \dot{X}_t) = M_s \ddot{X}_s \quad (3.12)$$

We use the following MATLAB model (Figure 1) to show the equation.

Figure 3.10: MATLAB model

3.3.2 Graphs for critical damping, over damping, and under damping

The damping coefficient affects the shape of the graph of the displacement. The critical damping coefficient is the minimum value of the damping coefficient that prevents oscillation. increasing the coefficient above this critical coefficient makes the system in **Over damping** state. Decreasing it under the critical coefficient makes the system in **Under damping state**.

The critical coefficient can be derived from the equation:

$$2\sqrt{km} = 2\sqrt{216.75 \times 21700} = 4337.5 N.s/m \quad (3.13)$$

Figures (3),(4), and (5) show the graph of displacement of each of the three states.

Figure 3.11: Under damping

Figure 3.12: Over damping

3.4 Question 2

3.4.1 The equation for the distance as a function of time

Figure (5) shows the graph of vertical displacement with respect to time.

3.4.2 Why does dumping coefficient affect the comfort of the driver

The damping coefficient affects the smoothness of the driving experience, and there is not really a specific coefficient that makes the driving experience better, it depends mainly on the mass, the spring constant and the amplitude of the road bumps, and by making different trials, it was found that in these specific conditions when the damping coefficient equals 3000, the resulted displacement is at its lowest, and consequently the driving experience is at its best.

Figure 3.13: Critical damping

Figure 3.14: Critical damping

Chapter 4

Non-linear RLC Circuit Projects

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4.1 Seif Mohamed, Omar Hassan

4.1.1 Problem 1

We will start by differentiating the equation with respect to time.

$$\Psi'(i) \frac{d^2 i}{dt^2} + \Psi''(i) \left(\frac{di}{dt}\right)^2 + \Gamma'(i) \frac{di}{dt} + \frac{1}{c} i = v_0 w \cos(wt)$$

$$[(L_1 + 3L_2 i^2 + 5L_3 i^4) \left(\frac{d^2 i}{dt^2}\right) + [20L_3 i^3 + 6L_2 i] \left(\frac{di}{dt}\right)^2 + [R_1 + 3R_2 i^2 + 5R_3 i^4] \left(\frac{di}{dt}\right) + \frac{1}{c} i = v_0 w \cos(wt)$$

4.1.2 Problem 2

solving the equation ,after substituting values for the constants, using scipy's odient and plotting the values of i and t using matplotlib resulted in the graph shown in figure(1)

Figure 4.1: current versus time graph

while plotting the values of the current and the change in current resulted in the graph shown in figure(2)

Figure 4.2: current versus change in current graph

4.1.3 Problem 3

graph in figure(3) was the result of changing the values of ω and V_o from 1 to π and $\frac{1}{\pi}$ respectively

Figure 4.3: current versus change in current graph

The frequency of the new graph is higher than the frequency of the original graph at the oscillating portion. due to multiplying the t inside the cos function by a value higher than 1 which is π .

4.1.4 Problem 4

the graphs shown below represents the three damping cases broadly known which are the under damped, the critical damped, the over damped. our system graphed in problem 2 shown in figure(1) seems to somehow have some similar aspects and differences with the graphs of the three cases that will be listed below

similarities:

- 1- our graph and the under damping graph share exhibiting very repetitive oscillatory behaviour
- 2- our graph and both critically and over damped graphs shows a very rapid response to the initial state as they both have a drastic drop from the initial values

differences:

- 1- the under damped oscillate regularly following simple harmonic motion while our graph has some intervals in which it behaves non-regularly such as the drastic drop at the beginning

- 2- In the under damped case, the amplitude and frequency of oscillations are determined by the linear parameters of the circuit (R, L, C). In the our case, the amplitude and frequency of oscillations may change with the current as well non-linearly.

- 3- the critically damped case follows a more uniform way of decaying while our graph can be more unpredictable due to its non-linearity

- 4- the critically and over damped cases doesn't oscillate while our graph exhibit oscillating behaviour

Figure 4.4: under damped oscillation

Figure 4.5: critical damped oscillation

Figure 4.6: over damped oscillation

4.1.5 Problem 5

The study of nonlinear RLC circuits is important for several reasons. As they are more realistic simulations of many real-world systems, differing from linear RLC circuits, in which the components (resistors, inductors, and capacitors) are assumed to be linear, i.e., their characteristics remains constant regardless of current strength. In reality, however, the components often exhibit nonlinear behavior due to factors such as temperature, and magnetic properties. The study of nonlinear RLC circuits is essential to understand and analyze these systems.

Another advantage of studying nonlinear RLC circuits is that they represent a variety of complex dynamics such as chaos. The study of chaos is essential for understanding and designing complex systems and analyze their seemingly unpredictable behavior, this could help in numerous applications from weather to financial markets to ecosystem dynamics. In order to be able to better predict and control such systems, studying more simple systems that exhibit chaos such as the non-linear RLC circuits provides tools to explore practical applications in various disciplines as well as fostering innovation and creativity in all sciences and arts stimulating innovation through computational ways. This research also contributes to fundamental scientific understanding by introducing concepts such as sensitivity to initial conditions and strange attractors.

RLC circuits locate commonplace use in real-life structures, one example is the Radio Tuning Circuit hired in AM (Amplitude Modulation) radios. This tuning circuit performs a pivotal role in enabling customers to pick out distinctive radio stations, and it achieves this by means of integrating RLC (Resistor, Inductor, and Capacitor) additives. These circuits facilitate the right selection of a particular radio frequency by using resonating at that unique frequency whilst actively rejecting others. It is the non-linear traits of RLC additives inside those circuits that are mainly vital, as they may be instrumental in demodulating the audio sign. This demodulation procedure guarantees that listeners hear the printed of their favored radio station, efficaciously filtering out any undesirable frequencies. The interaction between non-linear factors inside the tuning circuit is what underpins this remarkable frequency-selective behavior, enhancing the radio tuning experience for users.

4.2 Adam Mohamed, Ahmed ElKhatib, and Eyad Mohamed

4.2.1 Problem 1

Recall the equation depicting the voltage drop in a Non-Linear RLC Circuit:

$$\frac{d\Psi(i)}{dt} + \Gamma(i) + \frac{Q}{C} = V(t)$$

To get a differential equation that describes this system, particularly, the current intensity of the system, we need to transform every term into its equivalent formula regarding only current intensity. A direct substitution with the given functions of Ψ , Γ , and V would do so. However, this will not get rid of the Q in the equation. To get rid of the Q , we need to differentiate this whole equation with respect to t . This is because $\frac{dQ}{dt} = i$, which will give us the needed results.

Differentiating this equation is not trivial at all. So, let's first divide this equation into 4 parts (Ψ , Γ , $\frac{Q}{C}$, V) and differentiate each part separately.

Applying product and chain rules to find the second derivative of Ψ with respect to t yields:

$$\Psi(i) = L_1 i + L_2 i^3 + L_3 i^5$$

$$\frac{d\Psi}{dt} = L_1 \frac{di}{dt} + 3L_2 i^2 \frac{di}{dt} + 5L_3 i^4 \frac{di}{dt}$$

$$\frac{d^2\Psi}{dt^2} = L_1 \frac{d^2i}{dt^2} + 3L_2 (i^2 \frac{d^2i}{dt^2} + 2i (\frac{di}{dt})^2) + 5L_3 (i^4 \frac{d^2i}{dt^2} + 4i^3 (\frac{di}{dt})^2)$$

$$\frac{d^2\Psi}{dt^2} = (L_1 + 3L_2 i^2 + 5L_3 i^4) \frac{d^2i}{dt^2} + (6L_2 i + 20L_3 i^3) (\frac{di}{dt})^2$$

Applying product and chain rules to find the first derivative of Γ with respect to t yields:

$$\Gamma(i) = R_1 i + R_2 i^3 + R_3 i^5$$

$$\frac{d\Gamma}{dt} = R_1 \frac{di}{dt} + 3R_2 i^2 \frac{di}{dt} + 5R_3 i^4 \frac{di}{dt}$$

$$\frac{d\Gamma}{dt} = (R_1 + 3R_2 i^2 + 5R_3 i^4) \frac{di}{dt}$$

Applying the chain rule to find the first derivative of V with respect to t yields:

$$V(t) = V_o \sin(\omega t)$$

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = V_o \omega \cos(\omega t)$$

Lastly, the derivative of $\frac{Q}{C}$ with respect to t is $\frac{i}{C}$. Now, combining everything together:

$$V(t) = \frac{d\Psi(i)}{dt} + \Gamma(i) + \frac{Q}{C}$$

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = \frac{d^2\Psi}{dt^2} + \frac{d\Gamma}{dt} + \frac{d\frac{Q}{C}}{dt}$$

$$V_o\omega\cos(\omega t) = (L_1 + 3L_2i^2 + 5L_3i^4)\frac{d^2i}{dt^2} + (6L_2i + 20L_3i^3)\left(\frac{di}{dt}\right)^2 + (R_1 + 3R_2i^2 + 5R_3i^4)\frac{di}{dt} + \frac{i}{C}$$

which is the required differential equation to describe the system.

4.2.2 Problem 2

Graphing such a differential equation is difficult. Accordingly, computational aid has been utilized, specifically "Python". To see the procedures taken and the Python code, jump to **Page 30**.

Assuming that all constants are equal to 1 give the following graph for Current Intensity vs Time.

Figure 4.7: Current Intensity vs Time, All Constants = 1

As illustrated in **Figure 4.7**, the current intensity begins at a value of 1, which was the same as the stated initial conditions of the differential equation. Furthermore, the current intensity oscillates between a relative minimum value and a relative maximum value as time passes. The relative minimum value $\in (-0.75, -0.5)$, while the relative maximum value $\in (0.5, 0.75)$. Mainly, the cosine term in the differential equation is responsible for the oscillations. We can notice some nonlinearity at the beginning of the graph. This is mainly caused by the $(6L_2i + 20L_3i^3)(\frac{di}{dt})^2$ term in the differential equation.

The graph depicting the Change in Current Intensity vs Current Intensity is as shown below:

Figure 4.8: Change in Current Intensity vs Current Intensity, All Constants = 1

As illustrated in **Figure 4.8**, the initial values for the change in current intensity and current intensity are 0 and 1 respectively, which indeed follows the initial conditions stated in the differential equation. Furthermore, the change in current intensity also oscillates between two boundaries, forming a shape that is arguably similar to a circle. The relative maximum value for the change in current intensity approaches 1, and the relative minimum value for the change in current intensity approaches -1. This graph forms great synchronization with the previous graph, as both graphs suggest rational and identical behavior.

4.2.3 Problem 3

The graph of course varies by changing the value of the constants. Now, we will study the changes in the graph as the values of ω and V_o change.

Figure 4.9: Current Intensity vs Time, $V_o = \frac{1}{\pi}$

Figure 4.10: Change in Current Intensity vs Current Intensity, $V_o = \frac{1}{\pi}$

Figure 4.9 shows that V_o is directly proportional to the amplitude of oscillation. This indeed makes sense as the term $V_o\omega$ can be considered as the amplitude of the graph as the differential equation suggests, especially V_o . Therefore, when $V_o = \frac{1}{\pi}$, the amplitude decreased drastically compared to **Figure 4.7**. Accordingly, the change in the current vs current graph also changed as shown in **Figure 4.10**. It still oscillates but the boundaries or the relative minimum and maximum values for the change in the current intensity are different. The difference in the relative maximum and minimum values decreased.

Figure 4.11: Current Intensity vs Time, $\omega = \pi$

Figure 4.12: Change in Current Intensity vs Current Intensity, $\omega = \pi$

Figure 4.11 shows that ω is directly proportional to the number of oscillations per unit time. ω can be considered as the angular frequency of the system. Accordingly, when the value of ω was increased to π , the number of oscillations per unit time increased. At the beginning of the graph, the current intensity inconsistency and non-linearity increased, but as time passed it returned to normal oscillating behavior. The change in current intensity still oscillates between values that are near 1

and -1 as illustrated in **Figure 4.12**. However, it demonstrates inconsistency and non-linearity at the beginning of the graph because of the non-linearity at the beginning of **Figure 5**.

Figure 4.13: Current Intensity vs Time, $\omega = \pi$, $V_o = \frac{1}{\pi}$

Figure 4.14: Change in Current Intensity vs Current Intensity, $\omega = \pi$, $V_o = \frac{1}{\pi}$

Figure 4.13 and **Figure 4.14** show the current intensity vs time and change in current intensity vs current intensity respectively, but when $\omega = \pi$ and $V_o = \frac{1}{\pi}$. Indeed, the number of oscillations per unit of time increased because the value of ω increased. Furthermore, the inconsistencies at the beginning of the graph also increased. The amplitude also decreased because the value of V_o decreased.

4.2.4 Problem 4

The general differential equation depicting a damped oscillator is the following:

$$\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + 2\gamma\omega_n \frac{dx}{dt} + \omega_n^2 x = 0$$

where ω_n is the natural frequency of the system and γ is a constant. For $\gamma = 0$, the system isn't damped. If $0 < \gamma < 1$, the system is underdamped; if $\gamma = 1$, the system is critically damped; if $\gamma > 1$, the system is overdamped.

To be able to compare this simple damped system with the complex non-linear RLC circuit system, we will assume the same initial conditions for the damped system as the RLC circuit. Therefore, at $t = 0$, $x = 1$ and $\frac{dx}{dt} = 0$

For $\gamma = 0.1$, $\omega = 1$, the graph of the damped oscillator is as follows:

Figure 4.15: Underdamped Oscillator, $\gamma = 0.1$, $\omega = 1$

Figure 4.15 shows typical damped oscillator behavior. As time passes, the amplitude decreases. For greater values of γ that are less than 1, the amplitude will decrease more rapidly.

Now, we will show the similarities between **Figure 4.7** and **Figure 4.15**, in other words, the damped oscillator and the non-linear RLC circuit.

Similarities:

1. **Oscillations:** Both systems exhibit oscillations regardless of the nature of the oscillations, also both systems exhibit variations in the amplitude.
2. **Frequency Response:** The natural frequency (ω_n) of the damped oscillator and the frequency of the non-linear RLC circuit (ω) both impact the number of oscillations per unit of time.
3. **Amplitude Changes:** Both systems may exhibit amplitude variations.

Differences:

1. **Nature of oscillations:** Non-Linear RLC circuit can vary in amplitude at the beginning because of the term $(6L_2i + 20L_3i^3)(\frac{di}{dt})^2$, but after a certain amount of time it shows normal oscillations, while the damped oscillator shows exponential decay.
2. **Complexity:** The Non-Linear RLC circuit differential equation is far more complex than the differential equation for the damped oscillator. This leads to the major differences between both graphs.

Figure 4.16: Critically Damped Oscillator, $\gamma = 1$

Figure 4.16 shows typical critically damped oscillator behavior. The system does not oscillate but rather approaches but does not pass through its equilibrium position when it is released from rest. Now, we will demonstrate the similarities and differences between **Figure 4.16** and **Figure 4.7**.

Similarities:

1. **Initial Behaviour:** Both systems exhibit the same initial behavior as both functions at first are decreasing from their initial value.

Differences:

1. **General Behaviour:** The RLC circuit is oscillating. However, the critically damped oscillator does not exhibit oscillating behaviour but rather moves towards its equilibrium point as fast as possible when it is released from rest.

2. **Frequency:** The RLC circuit has angular frequency ω . However, the critically damped oscillator does not have a parameter called angular frequency.

Figure 4.17: Overdamped Oscillator, $\gamma = 2.3$

Figure 4.17 shows typical overdamped oscillator behaviour. The oscillator returns to its equilibrium position when it is released from rest. As the value of γ becomes greater, the oscillator takes more time to return to its equilibrium position. Now, we will demonstrate the similarities and differences between **Figure 4.17** and **Figure 4.7**.

Similarities:

1. **Initial Behaviour:** Both systems exhibit the same initial behaviour as both functions at first are decreasing from their initial value.

Differences:

1. **General Behaviour:** The RLC circuit is oscillating. However, the overdamped oscillator does not exhibit oscillating behaviour but rather moves slowly towards its equilibrium point when it is released from rest.

2. **Frequency:** The RLC circuit has angular frequency ω . However, the overdamped oscillator does not have a parameter called angular frequency.

4.2.5 Problem 5

There are many real-life applications for Non-Linear RLC Circuits. Here are 2 of them:

1. Oscillators: Non-linear RLC circuits can be combined with active components, such as transistors or operational amplifiers, to create oscillators that generate continuous, periodic waveforms. These oscillators intentionally produce nonsinusoidal output signals. The analysis of these types of oscillators is complicated by the fact that transform methods normally cannot be used. One frequently used technique for evaluating the performance of these types of oscillators is to determine the output and internal signals directly via time-domain calculations. For example, a function generator that produces square and triangle waves as its outputs combines an integrator with a Schmitt-trigger circuit.

2. Filters: Non-linear RLC circuits can be used as low-pass, high-pass, band-pass, or band-stop filters. These filters selectively pass or attenuate specific frequency ranges, making them ideal for signal-processing applications. The tuning application, for instance, is an example of band-pass filtering. The RLC filter is described as a second-order circuit, meaning that any voltage or current in the circuit can be described by a second-order differential equation in circuit analysis. In signal processing, a non-linear filter is a filter whose output is not a linear function of its input. Non-linear filters have many applications, especially in the removal of certain types of noise that are not additive. For example, the median filter is widely used to remove spike noise.

4.2.6 The Python Code

Python cannot directly graph a second-order differential equation. The second-order differential equation must be separated into 2 first-order ones. To do so, we followed these procedures:

Let $x_0 = i$ and $x_1 = \frac{di}{dt}$. Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned}x_1 &= \dot{x}_0 \\ \dot{x}_1 &= \ddot{x}_0 = \frac{d^2i}{dt^2}\end{aligned}$$

Now, the differential equation says that the value for $\frac{d^2i}{dt^2}$ is the following:

$$\frac{d^2i}{dt^2} = \frac{V_o \omega \cos(\omega t) - \left(\frac{di}{dt}\right)^2 (6L_2 i + 20L_3 i^3) - \frac{di}{dt} (R_1 + 3R_2 i^2 + 5R_3 i^4) - \frac{i}{C}}{L_1 + 3L_2 i^2 + 5L_3 i^4}$$

Substituting x_0 , x_1 :

$$\dot{x}_1 = \frac{V_o \omega \cos(\omega t) - x_1^2 (6L_2 x_0 + 20L_3 x_0^3) - x_1 (R_1 + 3R_2 x_0^2 + 5R_3 x_0^4) - \frac{x_0}{C}}{L_1 + 3L_2 x_0^2 + 5L_3 x_0^4}$$

From this, we can define a general function.

$$\dot{x} = f(x)$$

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} x_0 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$f(x) = \begin{bmatrix} V_0 \omega \cos(\omega t) - x_1^2 (6L_2 x_0 + 20L_3 x_0^3) - x_1 (R_1 + 3R_2 x_0^2 + 5R_3 x_0^4) - \frac{x_0}{C} \\ \frac{x_1}{L_1 + 3L_2 x_0^2 + 5L_3 x_0^4} \end{bmatrix}$$

where $f(x)$ and x are the stated arrays. Now, we can import this equation into Python and utilize libraries like Numpy, Matplotlib, and Scipy to solve and graph the differential equation.

The Code:

```

1 from scipy.integrate import odeint
2 import numpy as np
3 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
4 def moghni(x,t,w,v,l1,l2,l3,r1,r2,r3,c):
5     dxdt=[x[1],((v*w*np.cos(w*t)-(6*12*x[0]+20*13*pow(x[0],3))
6             *pow(x[1],2)-(r1+3*r2*pow(x[0],2)+5*r3*pow(x[0],4))
7             *x[1]-(x[0]/c)))/(11+3*12*pow(x[0],2)+5*13*pow(x[0],4))]
8     return dxdt
9 x0=[1,0]
10 timePoints=np.linspace(0,50,1500)
11 w=v=l1=l2=l3=r1=r2=r3=c=1
12 solutionOde=odeint(moghni,x0,timePoints, args=(w,v,l1,l2,l3,r1,r2,r3,c))
13 plt.plot(timePoints, solutionOde[:, 0], 'b', label=r'$i(t)$')
14 plt.legend(loc='best')
15 plt.xlabel('Time')
16 plt.ylabel("Current Intensity")
17 plt.ylim(-0.75, 1.25)
18 plt.grid()
19 plt.savefig('simulation.png')
20 plt.show()
21 plt.plot(solutionOde[:, 0], solutionOde[:, 1], 'g', label=r"$i'(t)$")
22 plt.legend(loc='best')
23 plt.xlabel('Current Intensity')
24 plt.ylabel("Change in Current Intensity")
25 plt.ylim(-1.5, 1.25)
26 plt.grid()
27 plt.savefig('simulation2.png')
28 plt.show()
29 v=1/np.pi
30 solutionOde=odeint(moghni,x0,timePoints, args=(w,v,l1,l2,l3,r1,r2,r3,c))
31 plt.plot(timePoints, solutionOde[:, 0], 'b', label=r'$i(t)$')
32 plt.legend(loc='best')
33 plt.xlabel('Time')
34 plt.ylabel("Current Intensity")
35 plt.grid()
36 plt.savefig('simulation13.png')
37 plt.show()
38 plt.plot(solutionOde[:, 0], solutionOde[:, 1], 'g', label=r"$i'(t)$")
39 plt.legend(loc='best')
40 plt.xlabel('Current Intensity')

```

```

41 plt.ylabel("Change in Current Intensity")
42 plt.grid()
43 plt.savefig('simulation14.png')
44 plt.show()
45 w=np.pi
46 v=1
47 solution0de=odeint(moghni,x0,timePoints, args=(w,v,l1,l2,l3,r1,r2,r3,c))
48 plt.plot(timePoints, solution0de[:, 0], 'b', label=r'$i(t)$')
49 plt.legend(loc='best')
50 plt.xlabel('Time')
51 plt.ylabel("Current Intensity")
52 plt.grid()
53 plt.savefig('simulation12.png')
54 plt.show()
55 plt.plot(solution0de[:, 0], solution0de[:, 1], 'g', label=r"$i'(t)$")
56 plt.legend(loc='best')
57 plt.xlabel('Current Intensity')
58 plt.ylabel("Change in Current Intensity")
59 plt.grid()
60 plt.savefig('simulation15.png')
61 plt.show()
62 w=np.pi
63 v=1/np.pi
64 l1=l2=l3=r1=r2=r3=c=1
65 solution0de=odeint(moghni,x0,timePoints, args=(w,v,l1,l2,l3,r1,r2,r3,c))
66 plt.plot(timePoints, solution0de[:, 0], 'b', label=r'$i(t)$')
67 plt.legend(loc='best')
68 plt.xlabel('Time')
69 plt.ylabel("Current Intensity")
70 plt.ylim(-0.4, 1.2)
71 plt.grid()
72 plt.savefig('simulation3.png')
73 plt.show()
74 plt.plot(solution0de[:, 0], solution0de[:, 1], 'g', label=r"$i'(t)$")
75 plt.legend(loc='best')
76 plt.xlabel('Current Intensity')
77 plt.ylabel("Change in Current Intensity")
78 plt.ylim(-0.6, 0.6)
79 plt.grid()
80 plt.savefig('simulation4.png')
81 plt.show()
82 def behaa(z,t,w_n,y):
83     dzdt=[z[1],(-pow(w_n,2)*z[0]-2*y*w_n*z[1])]
84     return dzdt
85 z0=[1,0]
86 timePoints2=np.linspace(0,50,1500)
87 w_n=1
88 y=0.1
89 solution0de2=odeint(behaa,z0,timePoints2, args=(w_n,y))
90 plt.plot(timePoints2, solution0de2[:, 0], 'b', label=r'$x(t)$')
91 plt.legend(loc='best')
92 plt.xlabel('Time')
93 plt.ylabel("Position " + r"$x(t)$")
94 plt.grid()
95 plt.savefig('simulation6.png')
96 plt.show()
97 w_n=1
    
```

```
98 y=1
99 solutionOde2=odeint(behaa,z0,timePoints2, args=(w_n,y))
100 plt.plot(timePoints2, solutionOde2[:, 0], 'b', label=r'$x(t)$')
101 plt.legend(loc='best')
102 plt.xlabel('Time')
103 plt.ylabel("Position " + r"$x(t)$")
104 plt.grid()
105 plt.savefig('simulation7.png')
106 plt.show()
107 w_n=1
108 y=2.3
109 solutionOde2=odeint(behaa,z0,timePoints2, args=(w_n,y))
110 plt.plot(timePoints2, solutionOde2[:, 0], 'b', label=r'$x(t)$')
111 plt.legend(loc='best')
112 plt.xlabel('Time')
113 plt.ylabel("Position " + r"$x(t)$")
114 plt.grid()
115 plt.savefig('simulation5.png')
116 plt.show()
```